

Managing Learning and Development

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Abstract

Training and development play an important role in the effectiveness of organization and to the experiences of people in work. Training has implications for productivity, health and safety at work and personal development. All organizations employing people need to train and develop their staff. Most organizations are cognizant of this requirement and invest effort and other resources in training and development. Such investment can take the form of employing specialist training and development. Investment in training and development entails aiming and development operational personal, employed in the organization's main business functions, such as production, maintenance, sales, marketing and management support, must also direct their attention and effort from time to time towards supporting training development and delivery. This means they are required to give less attention to activities that are obviously more productive in terms of the organization's main business. However investment in training and development generally regarded as good management practice maintain appropriate expertise now and in the future.

Introduction

Learning is another important psychological process determining human behavior. The human species. Unlike other animals, possess an extremely high proportion on unused mental capacity at birth. Human beings have very few instincts or innate response tendencies relative to lower animals. While this may be detrimental to man in the sense that he is helpless for a long period in his early years, it is favorable in the sense that he has greater capacity for adaption in response to changed survival condition. This is because of his learning capacity. As such, learning becomes an important concept in the study of human behavior.

Concept of Learning

Learning is a term frequently use by people in wide variety of contexts. Yet, despite its diverse use, at the academic level, its concept has been recognized in only one way, or at the most two, in which behavior can be acquired or changed. Early behaviorists like Watson and skinner have used learning as a relation or changed or association between two types of incidents. Based on this concept. The principle of conditioning has been developed which we shall see later in this chapter. However, many psychologists do not agree with this view

and they have viewed learning as a relatively enduring change in behavior. This view is more acceptable. According to the dictionary of psychology, learning means “the process of acquiring the ability to respond adequately to a situation which may not have been previously encountered, the favorable modification of response tendencies consequent upon previous experience, particularly the building of a new series of complex coordinated motor response; the fixation of items in memory so that they can be recalled organized; the process of acquiring insight into a situation”

Sanford has defined learning as a relatively enduring change in behavior brought about as a consequence of experience. In the context of organizational behavior too, learning is defined in this way. In this text, we shall take learning as a relatively enduring change in behavior to experience.

Nature of Learning

Based on the definition of learning, we may identify the following nature of learning.

Learning involves a change in behavior; through this change is not necessarily an improvement over previous behavior. Learning generally has the connotation of improved behavior, but bad habits, prejudices, stereotypes, and work restrictions are also learned.

The behavioral change must be relatively permanent. Any temporary change in behavior due to fatigue or any reason is not a part of learning.

The behavioral change must be relatively permanent. Any temporary change in behavior because of physical maturation is not learning. For instance, the ability to work which is based on physical maturation would not be considered learning.

The practice or experience must be reinforced in order for learning to occur. If reinforcement does not accompany the practice or experience, the behavior will disappear.

Components of Learning Process

A person receives a variety of stimulus inputs. When specific stimuli become associated with specific response in a sufficiently permanent manner that the occurrence of the stimuli elicits or tends to elicit a particular response, learning has occurred. To understand this process, it is important to understand the role of various components. These components are drive, cue stimuli, response, reinforcement and retention.

1. Drive
2. Cue Stimuli
3. Generalization
4. Discrimination
5. Response
6. Reinforcement
7. Retention
8. Spontaneous Recovery

Learning Organization

Ideally, all organizations must develop their personnel to meet changing environmental requirements. However, all organizations are not alike in terms of developing their personnel to adapt to environmental requirements. Some organizations take proactive action in the light of anticipated environmental changes: some take reactive actions based on environmental changes; and some do not react at all to environmental changes. The organizations which fall in the first category

anticipate likely changes in the environment and gear their human resource to face environmental threats that like to be posed. Such organization emphasizes continuous organizational learning and is known as learning organization. Two terms, organizational learning and learning organization are effectively synonymous but their nuance differs. While organizational learning is a process, a set of action, learning organization is an entity. Garvin has defined a learning organization as follows: These characteristics are:

Benefits of Learning Organization

The major benefits of learning organization are as follows:

1. Maintaining high level of innovation.
2. Improving quality of outputs at all organization levels.
3. Being better able to respond to external pressures.
4. Having the knowledge to better link its resources to customer need.
5. Improving corporate image by becoming more people oriented.
6. Increasing the pace of change within the organization.

Chen et al., 2008: Distance education, its delivery is typically delivered by enterprise wide learning management system which have become integral to university teaching and learning environments (Rankine, Stevenson, Malfroy, & Ashford Rowe, 2009). LMS are software system that synthesize the functionality of computer-mediated communications software system that synthesize the functionality of computer-mediated communication software and online methods of delivering course activities and materials (Jennings, 2005). Coates and Baldwin (2005) state that LMS Influence engagement is still in its infancy

(West, Waddoups, & Graham, 2006): This paper says being used for presenting online or technology-enhanced classes and it has been said that they influence pedagogy and therefore engagement by presenting default formats that are designed to guide instructors towards creating courses in certain ways (Lane, 2009). If LMS are affecting pedagogy, then they are likely to be affecting study habits, learning and engagement (Coates et al, 2005)

Hoskins, S.L. and Van Hooff (2005): Aimed to determine whether the approaches to studying, ability, age, and gender of 10 undergraduates in the second year of psychology degree predicted extent to which they utilized online learning using an LMS like WebCT found that only bulletin board use influenced achievement, with those posting messages out performing those not using, or passively using bulletin boards. However, because individual difference will determine the extent to which student utilize the facility, it is suggested that future utilize this facilities'

Curtis and Lawson (2008): In their study found that there is evidence that successful collaboration as described in face-to-face situation is possible in online learning environment. The medium does influence the interaction that are possible and that student familiarity with the medium and the ease of use of the important factors. Instruction for the student in the use software and better preparation for the challenging of collaborative.

Conclusion

The pace at which science proceed sometime seems alarmingly slow, and impatience and hopes both run high when discussions turn to learning, the past quarter century has been a period of the many new development, the studies that resulted in this volume were conducted to appraise the scientific knowledge base on human learning and its application to education. We evaluated the best and most current scientific data on learning, teaching, and learning environments. The objective of the analysis was to ascertain what is required for learners to reach deep understanding, to determine what leads to effective teaching, and to evaluate the condition that lead to supportive environments for teaching and learning.

A scientific understanding of learning includes understanding about learning process, learning environments, teaching, socio cultural process, and the many other factor that contributed to learning. Research on all of these topic, both in the field and in laboratories, provides are the fundamental knowledge base for understanding and implementing changes in education.